

THE IMPACT OF CHAT GPT ON STUDENT'S WRITING SKILLS: AN EXPLORATION OF AI-ASSISTED WRITING TOOLS

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Abstract: This article explores the ways in which Chat GPT, an AI-assisted writing tool, can impact student's writing skills. Chat GPT can assist students with generating writing prompts, providing feedback and revision suggestions, and offering writing assistance. The article discusses the benefits and potential drawbacks of using Chat GPT for improving student's writing skills, as well as provides examples of how this technology is being used in education. These examples include the University of Michigan's AI writing tutor M-Write and AI-powered writing assistants like Grammarly and Hemingway Editor. While Chat GPT has the potential to transform the way we teach writing, further research is needed to evaluate the effectiveness of this technology in improving student's writing skills.

Key words: writing skills, AI, Chat GPT, feedback, writing tool, education, technology.

Abstract: Ushbu maqola sun'iy idrokka asoslangan yozish vositasi bo'lgan Chat GPT talabalarning yozish ko'nikmalariga qanday ta'sir qilishi mumkinligini o'rganadi. Chat GPT talabalarga yozish bo'yicha ko'rsatmalar berish, qayta ko'rib chiqish bo'yicha takliflar berish hamda to'liq yozish jaraonida yordam berishi mumkin. Maqolada talabalarning yozish ko'nikmalarini oshirish uchun Chat GPT dan foydalanishning afzalliklari va mumkin bo'lgan kamchiliklari muhokama qilinadi, shuningdek, ushbu texnologiya ta'limda qanday qo'llanilishiga misollar keltiriladi. Bu misollar orasida Michigan universitetining M-Write va Grammarly va Hemingway Editor kabi sun'iy intellektga asoslangan yozuv yordamchilari kiradi. Chat GPT yozishni o'rgatish bo'yicha hozirgi uslublarimizni o'zgartirish

imkoniyatiga ega bo'lsa-da, talabalarning yozish ko'nikmalarini oshirishda ushbu texnologiyaning samaradorligini baholash uchun qo'shimcha tadqiqotlar talab etiladi.

The rise of artificial intelligence (AI) has impacted virtually every aspect of modern life, and education is no exception. One area where AI is increasingly being used is in the evaluation of student writing. Chat GPT, an AI-powered language model, can be a powerful tool to help students improve their writing skills. Chat GPT can provide students with writing prompts, generate feedback on their writing, and even suggest ways to improve their writing style. In this article, we will explore the ways in which Chat GPT can be used to improve students' writing skills, and provide examples of how this technology is being used in education. This article will also focus on potential drawbacks AI-based writing tools can have on students' writing process.

Although introduction of Chat GPT in November 2022 has gained some negative criticism from general public in terms of writing, the advantages this writing tool can offer for educational purposes should not be overlooked. Here are some ways in which Chat GPT can positively impact students' writing process:

1. Writing prompts

Writing prompts are a great way to get students started on a writing task. However, coming up with engaging and challenging prompts can be time-consuming for teachers. Chat GPT can help by generating a wide range of writing prompts on different topics, genres, and formats. For example, students can use Chat GPT to generate prompts for a descriptive essay on a particular location, a persuasive essay on a current event, or a creative writing piece on a fictional character. This variety can help students to develop their writing skills in different areas and expand their writing repertoire.

2. Feedback and Revision

Feedback is an essential aspect of the writing process. It helps students identify areas of strength and weakness in their writing and make improvements

accordingly. Chat GPT can provide instant feedback on a student's writing, highlighting areas that need improvement, such as grammar, spelling, and punctuation. Additionally, Chat GPT can provide suggestions for revision, helping students to refine their writing style and structure. For example, if a student's essay is unclear or lacks coherence, Chat GPT can suggest changes in sentence structure or organization that can improve the essay's flow and readability. Revision is an essential part of the writing process, and Chat GPT can help students revise their work effectively. By using Chat GPT's feedback and revision suggestions, students can learn to identify and correct writing errors and improve their overall writing skills. However, Chat GPT is not the only AI tool that is being used to provide feedback for writing. 'WriteLab is an example of a digital platform that promises "Immediate Feedback. Revision Mastery. Measurable Growth" on its website. This program of "instant AI-assisted feedback powered by Natural Language Processing that refines and strengthens student writing," is endorsed by Forbes Magazine and Stanford University, among many others ("WriteLab and Chegg: Improve your writing in less time").'¹

3. Writing Assistance

Chat GPT can be a valuable resource for students who struggle with writing, such as students with learning disabilities or non-native speakers of English. Chat GPT can provide writing assistance, such as suggesting alternative words or phrases that convey a similar meaning. Additionally, Chat GPT can provide explanations of grammar rules or provide examples of how to use specific words or phrases in context. This can be particularly helpful for students who need additional support with their writing.

Such opportunities Chat GPT offer have not been neglected by leading educational institutions worldwide. Here we can see some examples of Chat GPT in education.

¹ [walker.pdf \(colostate.edu\)](#)

Chat GPT is already being used in education to help students improve their writing skills. For example, the University of Michigan has developed an AI writing tutor called M-Write that uses Chat GPT to provide students with feedback on their writing. M-Write provides students with writing prompts, feedback on their writing, and revision suggestions. This technology has been shown to improve students' writing skills and increase their confidence in their writing ability. 'Despite the trepidations of commenters like those above, this author wishes to consider the affordances that AI robo-tutor might achieve. Programs such as WriteLab, M-Write, Eli Review, and others are already doing this work to some degree.'²

Another example of Chat GPT in education is the use of AI-powered writing assistants such as Grammarly and Hemingway Editor. These tools use Chat GPT to analyze students' writing and provide suggestions for improvement, such as correcting grammar and punctuation errors and suggesting changes in sentence structure. These tools can be used by students independently or in conjunction with writing instruction from their teachers.

However much we praise this AI based writing tool, not everyone is positive about the influence of it on writing overall. There are also concerns about the impact of AI on student writing skills. Some worry that the use of AI will discourage students from learning how to write well. If students are relying on AI to correct their mistakes, they may not learn how to identify and correct those mistakes on their own. Additionally, there is a risk that students will become overly reliant on AI and fail to develop critical thinking skills and creativity.

'A high school student in Britain echoed the same concern about individual writing style when describing Grammarly: "Grammarly can remove students' artistic voice. ... Rather than using their own unique style when writing, Grammarly can strip that away from students by suggesting severe changes to their work."³

² [walker.pdf \(colostate.edu\)](#)

³ [How ChatGPT robs students of motivation to write and think for themselves \(theconversation.com\)](#)

Researchers have also found some profound effects writing process has on our intellectual well-being. Some worry that rise of Chat GPT as a writing tool will deprive people of the advantages the writing process offer to our brains:

‘Furthermore, the better one becomes at writing, the better they become at both critical thinking and creative problem solving. Writing also improves our recall, since putting pen to paper helps transition information from short term to long term memory.’⁴

Another concern is that AI may reinforce bias in writing evaluation. AI algorithms are only as good as the data they are trained on, and if that data is biased, the algorithm will be biased as well. For example, if an AI algorithm is trained on a dataset of writing that is predominantly written by white, male authors, it may have difficulty evaluating writing that is written by authors from different backgrounds. ‘It is no surprise that an AI chat bot like ChatGPT can generate [biased](#) responses. But AI technology only mirrors what has been programmed and what it has been trained on. We may be far from the point where we can truly rely on the responses generated from any AI system.’⁵

In conclusion, the rise of artificial intelligence has had a significant impact on student writing skills. While there are potential benefits to using AI in writing instruction, there are also concerns about the negative effects it may have on students' ability to learn and develop their writing skills. As with any technology, it is essential to use AI in a responsible and thoughtful way, taking into account both its benefits and drawbacks. Ultimately, the goal should be to use AI as a tool to supplement and enhance writing instruction, rather than as a substitute for it.

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